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DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL STANDARDS FOR ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN UKRAINE

Professional standards are developed based on the most popular types of labor (professional) activities, professions, and qualifications that are in demand in the labor market. Note that Ukraine has the second-highest number of IT specialists among CEE countries. Ukraine ranked second in terms of the number of AI companies among Central and Eastern European countries, second only to Poland. At the end of 2023, there were 243 AI companies in Ukraine and 301 in Poland. In third place after Ukraine is Estonia, with 154 companies, according to a study by AI House and Roosh. Since 2020, the number of AI companies in Ukraine has grown by 34% [1]. The number of AI specialists in Ukraine has increased fivefold in ten years and is 5,200 professionals as of January 2024. Professional standards are the basis for developing educational standards, methodological materials, and professional training programs for employees. It is in the professional standard that the criteria for the quality of personnel training are established. They are mandatory for consideration when developing educational standards and have become a full-fledged replacement for qualification characteristics. Thus, developing professional standards in artificial intelligence is an urgent need in Ukraine. It should be noted that professional standards with appropriate requirements for knowledge, skills, and abilities have already been developed and successfully applied by both employers and the educational sphere in such developed countries as the United States of America (USA), United Kingdom (UK), etc. Taking into account international experience, some legislative norms were adopted in Ukraine and in 2017-2023 a methodology for developing professional standards in Ukraine was developed. The European standards for AI, as outlined in the EU AI Act [2], have now become a global benchmark for regulating the development and deployment of AI technologies.

For Ukraine, the implementation of the EU AI Act is important, because we are a candidate for the EU, and the law introduces a single system for all European countries. Currently, Ukraine does not have a legislative framework. The AI ecosystem of Ukraine, comprising various organizations and technologies working together within the field of AI, needs to transform integration with the European Union [3]. Scientists led by the Institute of Artificial Intelligence Problems have developed a “Strategy for Artificial Intelligence development in Ukraine” [4]. National Qualifications Agency (NQA) is a permanent collegiate body that performs the functions defined by the Law of Ukraine "On Education" and other legislative acts in the field of qualifications. NQA accredits Qualification Centers, that provide the possibility to validate the qualification based on formal, non-formal, or informal education and training acquired in Ukraine

or abroad. Also, NQA coordinates the development of occupational standards that would meet modern labor market requirements, maintains a register of occupational standards and a register of qualifications, and coordinates the subjects of the professional improvement process of training, retraining, and establishing compliance with occupational standards. Currently, there are no professional standards in artificial intelligence in the NQA-registry [5]. To implement the Action Plan for the Implementation of the National Qualification Framework, approved by the order of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine to develop draft professional standards "Artificial Intelligence Systems Development Specialist" and "Artificial Intelligence Application Specialist", the International Professional Qualifications Agency created a working group in 2024. Work has begun on the creation of these professional standards. Professional standards are based on ISO standards and ESCO. The working group of developers of professional standards on AI in Ukraine works following the Procedure for developing professional standards [6] and Methodological recommendations for the development of professional standards [7]. When developing a draft professional standard, an analysis of activity by profession is performed, which combines methodological approaches based on functional analysis, analysis of the workplace, scope of tasks, work processes and environment, etc. The working group plans to complete the development of professional standards by the end of 2025.

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